

"BOBURNOMA" CREATOR AS MAIN EPISODE

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the writing of the famous "Boburnoma" written by the great king and poet Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, his fame, and the role of the writer as the main character in the work. Also, special emphasis is given to the circumstances that reflected the virtues and generosity of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur has the title of king and poet, unparalleled writer and historian among the eternal great children of mankind. In the history of humanity, there are very few people with exceptional personal capabilities, talents and qualities like Baburcha. Babur's fame as a classical poet is not only in our country, but also worldwide. However, the work that brought world fame to Babur is not his "Devon", "Mubayyin" or "Aruz risolasi", but "Boburnoma", more precisely, his translations into different languages.

How high the influence of the Persian language and literature was in Khorasan and Movarunnahr, India and Afghanistan, Iran and Turkey in the 15th - 16th centuries can be explained by the words of the writer and translator of "Boburnoma": "translation of the work into Persian from India to Turkey. It was the belief that it reached the peoples and intellectuals of the huge area, the secretary is writing referring to "Boburnoma". Let me bring your Turkish to Persia, make it easy for people who don't know Turkish."

Rashid Akhtar, who translated "Boburnoma" again into Persian, writes about the first Persian translation of Abdurahim Khani Khanon, the son of Nadvi Bayram Khan, "After that, the people of the world, for the first time, used the words of the great crown prince (Babur). He found out that he was a Shahanshihi.

Shah, writer, poet, army chief Babur's work "Vaqoye" ("Events"), later known as "Boburnoma", is a diary account of an important part of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's conscious life and work. That's why the poet writes about this work and its relevance to his biography in one rubai.

Bu olam aro ajab alamlar ko`rdum,
Olam elidinturfa sitamlar ko`rdum,
Har kim bu "Vaqoye"ni o`qur, bilgaykim
Ne ranj-u, ne mehnat-u, ne g`amlar ko`rdum.

"Boburnoma" is, first of all, a mature work of art. The interpretations typical of artistic images, the ability to embody events and events with all their reality in front of the reader's eyes, artistic work on words, the strength of style - one feature of this style is the generosity of thought and concise description, and the second feature is its uniqueness and, most importantly, the priority of effectiveness. Although the author modestly refrains from putting himself forward in the text by saying "ordered" instead of "I ordered", Babur himself is the main character of the work. will remain. In the world of events in Ferghana, Kabul and India, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's great personality is clearly visible. The following comments of the English orientalist Monstuart Elphinstone about "Boburnoma" and its main character are noteworthy: "In these memoirs, the life of the great Turkish king is described in detail, his personal feelings are free from any exaggeration and veiling. His style is simple and brave, lively and figurative. He describes the faces, traditions, aspirations, actions of his contemporaries as clearly as a mirror, and in this respect, this work is the only example of a truly historical image in Central Asia. Babur describes the appearance, clothes, taste and habits of a military man, describes the countries, their climate, nature, economy, art and crafts. But the bright character of the author gives the work the most charm."

In a certain sense, the events in the work are closely related to the fateful adventures of the writer. Therefore, the reader who has read the book from beginning to end can clearly imagine Babur as a teenager, as a young prince, as a lover, as a king and thinker, as a loving father, as a lifelong warlord, with all his qualities and defects. From the day he took the pen in hand, the author decided to write "Vaqoye" ("Boburnoma") only the truth about the interpretation of events and the opinions and information about the personalities of people (transcription) "It was I wrote the events correctly. Because in this work, it is necessary that the truth of every word is written and every action is told exactly as it happened." That is why Babur tries to tell all his important qualities and character defects when evaluating each person. In this, he does not allow exceptions, even if he is a father, he follows those two necessary measures. Not only to his father, but also to himself.

According to V. Rahmanov, Babur is perfect in several ways.

First of all, magnanimity in kindness and generosity of gifts not only to one's own relatives, but also to strangers,

secondly, the ability to objectively and completely assess the personality of anyone, friend or foe,

thirdly, the indefatigable flag bearer of Sharia, Sharia protection, (the ability to assess and judge every social-political, moral situation, not to retreat from it,

fourth, physical maturity (for example, in the village of Hashtiyak, he takes a bath many times in a deep, fast-flowing stream whose banks are frozen) (translated from the text) "I needed a bath. the whites were covered with thick ice, and the water in the middle did not freeze due to the speed of the water, so I entered this water and took a bath. fifthly, he was the owner of the highest level of forgiveness characteristic of a Muslim. After a year, Mirza Khan returned and was accepted into the ranks of Babur's trusted and important people.

sixthly, maturity of thought in every field - thinking was characteristic of him. Socio-political events, moral problems, even in the field of literary studies.

Since "Baburnoma" is a work of art, the analysis of its main character, Babur, is, in our opinion, very important. Therefore, another invaluable value of the work is that with its help, the creative biography of Babur and the history of his works can be easily restored. For example, the author "When he was in this Mascho, the poet Mullah Hijri came to visit Hisar. I said this matla in these days

Takalluf har necha sur`at tutilsa, ondin ortuqsen

Seni jon derlar, ammo betakalluf jondin ortuqsen

- admits. He remembers that he was in Tashkent with his uncle Mahmud Khan, and writes "I recited this rubai, there was a hesitation in the rhyme of Mamul, I did not aspire to the independence of the poem in that place, the Khan was a pleasant person, if only the straw "The age was less. "Then I found out that "to" and "dol", "gain" and "qof" and "kof" are used in Turkish "they share each other".

Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur is, first of all, a brave person. This quality, especially, such people as Babur, whose destiny is complex and multifaceted, quickly puts him to various tests. Because courage is tested more severely not only with friends, but also with enemies.

Many events in "Boburnoma" repeatedly show the celebration of this brave character of Babur. Because when the khans went on a military campaign together with Babur with the intention of capturing Andijan and Akhsi, Shay Bayazid, the fortress beg of Akhsi, invited Babur. Babur's uncle asked Sultan Mahmud Khan and the younger khan - Olacha Khan for advice about this through one person. Khans say "Let's go. Whatever he does, let Shay catch Bayazid." This makr-u-firib was not our custom and method. Alalkhususkim, there is a covenant between them. What is the violation of such a contract?"

We are witnesses that even in any difficult situation, Babur's bravery and loyalty to his covenant are clearly demonstrated. Courage is known to give priority to covenants and stipulations, and it also manifests itself in seeing extremely difficult physical sufferings as an equal to oneself.

Babur's pen was sharp in various subjects and genres. Sahli mumtane' - he wrote wonderful ghazals in the ancient style of narration, which looks easy and sounds lively, but in reality, such writing is difficult. We will enjoy a good example of it below

Ey yuzi nasrin, qomati shamshod,

Necha qilursen jonima bedod.

Sen kibi purkor, shevasi bisyor,

Bilmadi, ey yor, hech kishi yod.

Javrda nodir, zulmda mohir,

Ishvada qodir, g`amzada ustod.

Yor g`amidin, hajr alamidin,

Sabr kamidin nola-yu faryod.

Boburi bedil, ey buti qotil,

Javrunga moyil, zulmunga mu`tod.

Conclusion . The more analysis is done about the importance of "Boburnoma" and the qualities of its creator, the less research is conducted. We quote the comments of the English Babur scholar Lane Poole about this. personal impressions and subtle thoughts about the world of the owner of an impressionable soul who can think justly are given. His sincerity in

drawing his image, bravely portraying his virtues and defects, his frankness, truthfulness and great sense of humor increase the value and importance of these beautiful memories." Babur's life path, the events he went through, the non-stop trials full of excitement, the days he spent wandering away from his homeland, are now in the distant history. But its warmth accompanies us every minute thanks to "Baburnoma". The virtues and deeds of its creator, main character Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur are an example for all of us. Our hearts are full of pride that we have such an ancestor.

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